

Determinants Influencing Healthcare Facility Selection and Patient Contentment

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Abstract : This study explores the determinants of healthcare facility selection and patient contentment in the Pondicherry district. As healthcare systems become more patient-centered, understanding these factors is crucial for improving service delivery and patient outcomes. Key determinants include accessibility, quality of care, cost, infrastructure, and personal recommendations. **Materials and Methods:** A descriptive research design was employed, utilizing a structured questionnaire for data collection from patients at private and public hospitals in Pondicherry. A pilot study confirmed the reliability of the instrument, achieving a Cronbach's Alpha value above 0.8. Stratified random sampling yielded a sample size of 384, with 387 valid responses analyzed using central tendency measures, dispersion, and regression analysis to identify factors affecting patient satisfaction. **Results:** The study identified that doctor's qualifications and hospital reputation significantly impact healthcare facility selection, while quality of care and patient experience influence patient contentment. However, hospital facilities and services did not directly affect healthcare facility selection, nor did facility selection influence patient contentment. **Conclusion:** Improving healthcare services requires addressing doctor qualifications, modernizing facilities, enhancing accessibility, and fostering community engagement. These efforts can lead to better patient satisfaction and healthcare outcomes. **Originality:** This study provides a nuanced understanding of the determinants of healthcare facility selection and patient contentment, highlighting the importance of specific factors such as doctor qualifications and hospital reputation in influencing patient choices and satisfaction. By focusing on these elements, the research offers valuable insights for enhancing healthcare service delivery and outcomes in the Pondicherry district.

Key Words: Healthcare Facility Selection, Patient Contentment, Accessibility, Quality of Care, Descriptive Research, Patient Satisfaction, Healthcare Services

Introduction

This research explores factors affecting patient choice and satisfaction in healthcare facilities. Key determinants include accessibility, quality of care, and cost. Accessible locations attract more patients, while high-quality care and affordable services enhance satisfaction (O'Donnell & Gardner, 2021; Choi, 2018). Facility infrastructure and personal recommendations also play significant roles. Demographics like age, gender, and socio-economic status influence healthcare preferences (Javed, 2020; Aarons, 2015). The study uses both quantitative and qualitative methods, including surveys and interviews, to identify patterns influencing patient decisions (Shen & Xu, 2020). Findings will help healthcare providers and policymakers improve services by enhancing accessibility, investing in infrastructure, and making care more affordable (Yoo & Park, 2021). Prioritizing patient needs and preferences is crucial for effective healthcare delivery and increased patient satisfaction (Basak & Paul, 2021).

1. What is Healthcare Facility Selection?

Healthcare facility selection involves choosing a provider based on factors such as quality of care, location, services offered, cost, and personal recommendations (**Haque, 2018**). Accessibility is vital, with patients preferring facilities that are convenient and easy to reach. The quality of care includes the facility's reputation, specialized services, and patient experience (**Kim & Choi, 2019**). Cost is crucial, especially when out-of-pocket expenses are involved; facilities with competitive pricing and financial assistance attract cost-sensitive patients (**Afsar, Badar, & Ullah, 2021**). Personal recommendations and experiences also play a significant role, enhancing a facility's reputation. Overall, understanding these factors is essential for improving healthcare delivery and patient satisfaction (**Dewit, 2016**).

2. What is Patient Contentment?

Patient contentment, or satisfaction, is a vital measure of healthcare quality from the patient's viewpoint. It includes the overall experience from initial contact to treatment completion (**Lee, 2018**). Key factors are the accessibility and convenience of services, quality of care, facility environment, and interactions with providers (**Ahmed & Nawaz, 2017**). High patient contentment correlates with better outcomes, increased loyalty, and adherence to treatment plans. Timely appointments, clear communication, compassionate care, and effective pain management enhance satisfaction (**Saxena, 2016**). Personalized care that respects patient preferences fosters trust and comfort (**Nayyar, 2018**). Overall, patient contentment reflects how well services meet or exceed expectations and is crucial for guiding improvements in healthcare delivery (**Foster, 2017**).

3. Aim of the Study

This research aims to explore the key factors affecting patient selection of healthcare facilities and their satisfaction levels. It focuses on determinants such as accessibility, quality of care, cost, and provider reputation (**Wang & Wang, 2022**), and examines their relationship with patient satisfaction, including both subjective and objective outcomes. The study seeks to understand patient priorities and expectations to provide insights for improving service delivery and patient satisfaction. The findings will guide healthcare policymakers and administrators in developing patient-centered strategies and interventions, enhancing health outcomes and contributing to the knowledge base on healthcare management and patient care optimization (**Park & Kim, 2022**).

4. Need for the Study

The healthcare sector is vital for public health, and understanding what influences healthcare facility selection and patient satisfaction is essential. This study addresses a gap in literature by examining factors such as accessibility, quality of care, cost, staff behavior, and facility infrastructure (**Murray & Wicht, 2018; Luo & Zhao, 2015; Andaleeb, 2015**). Identifying these determinants will help healthcare providers and policymakers improve service delivery, patient outcomes, and strategic planning, enhancing patient satisfaction and equity in healthcare access (**Wong & Chan, 2019; Cheng, 2019**). The study aims to offer insights that benefit both providers and patients.

5. Statement of the Problem

Understanding the factors influencing patients' selection of healthcare facilities and their satisfaction is vital for enhancing healthcare services and outcomes (Erdogan & Bayraktar, 2022). Despite numerous healthcare options, patients often struggle to identify facilities that meet their needs effectively (Narayan & Choudhury, 2019). This decision-making complexity is shaped by various determinants, including the quality of care, accessibility, cost, provider reputation, and personal recommendations (Tuzunkan, 2020). Patient satisfaction, a critical quality metric, affects retention, adherence, and health outcomes (Younis, 2018). This research aims to identify and analyze these key determinants and their impact on patient satisfaction (Zhang & Zhao, 2020). Insights from this study will guide healthcare providers in refining service delivery and enhancing patient experiences, contributing to better health outcomes (Osei, 2017). By examining the relationship between facility choice and patient satisfaction, the study will offer actionable recommendations for policymakers to develop more patient-centered healthcare systems (Sarma & Ghosh, 2021).

6. Objective of the Study

The research aims to elucidate the pivotal determinants affecting patients' choice of healthcare facilities and their satisfaction. By examining factors such as care quality, accessibility, cost, provider reputation, and personal endorsements, it seeks to provide nuanced insights for refining service delivery and optimizing patient-centered healthcare systems.

7. Conceptual Model

The conceptual model illustrates the relationships between key determinants such as quality of care, accessibility, cost, provider reputation, and personal recommendations, and their impact on healthcare facility selection and patient contentment. This model serves as a framework for understanding and improving patient-centered healthcare decision-making and satisfaction.

Figure.1. Impact of Factors Influencing Healthcare Facility Selection on Patient Contentment

8. Methodology of the Study

This study uses a descriptive research design to explore the determinants influencing healthcare facility selection and patient contentment in the Pondicherry district. Descriptive research is well-suited for this investigation as it aims to describe characteristics and behaviors of the target population without modifying the environment (Sekaran & Bougie, 2019; Barua,

Akter & Islam, 2021). The study began with a pilot test involving 50 respondents to assess the reliability and validity of the research instrument. A Cronbach's Alpha value exceeding 0.8 confirmed high internal consistency, ensuring the reliability of the variables related to healthcare facility selection and patient contentment (**Swain & Sen, 2018; Donabedian, 2016**). Validity was assessed through both content and construct validity. Content validity was established by conducting a thorough literature review and consulting with healthcare experts to ensure that the questionnaire items accurately reflected the constructs of quality of care, accessibility, cost, provider reputation, and personal recommendations (**Mosadeghrad, 2020; Sekaran & Bougie, 2019**). Construct validity was assessed using exploratory factor analysis (EFA), which demonstrated that each of the variables loaded appropriately on their respective factors, confirming that the items measured the intended constructs (**Li & Hu, 2021; Ha, Berman & Larsen, 2020; Liu & Fang, 2022**).

Data collection was carried out through a structured questionnaire distributed among patients at both private and public hospitals in Pondicherry (**Swain & Sen, 2018**). The questionnaire included demographic questions and items assessing factors affecting healthcare facility selection and measures of patient contentment. A stratified random sampling method was employed, dividing the population into subgroups based on hospital type and drawing proportional samples from each subgroup (**Sekaran & Bougie, 2019; Atinga, Abekah-Nkrumah & Domfeh, 2021**). According to the De Morgan sample size estimator, a sample size of approximately 384 was determined, considering a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error (**Swain & Sen, 2018; Ghavami & Tavakoli, 2019**). The researcher distributed 400 questionnaires (200 to private hospitals and 200 to government hospitals) and received 190 responses from private hospitals and 197 from government hospitals, totaling 387 valid responses after excluding 13 biased entries. Data analysis utilized measures of central tendency and dispersion to summarize data and regression analysis to identify significant predictors of patient contentment (**Alhassan et al., 2022; Ashraf et al., 2019**). This approach provided insights into factors influencing patient satisfaction and offered a robust framework for enhancing healthcare services in Pondicherry (**Calnan & Sanford, 2021; Kruk & Freedman, 2017**). Ethical considerations, including participant confidentiality and informed consent, were strictly followed throughout the study (**Sekaran & Bougie, 2019; Zhou & Tan, 2022**).

Results and Discussion

In analyzing healthcare facility selection and patient contentment, measures of central tendency (mean) and dispersion (standard deviation) summarized data variability. Regression analysis identified predictors impacting patient contentment, clarifying which aspects of facility selection influence satisfaction. This blend of statistics offered a robust framework for understanding these dynamics in the study.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics - Healthcare Facility Selection & Patient Contentment

Healthcare Facility Selection	Mean	Sd	Patient Contentment	Mean	Sd
Doctor’s Qualification & Experience	2.32	.471	Quality of Medical Care	3.96	.198
Hospital Facilities & Services	2.08	.274	Patient Experience & Access	1.96	.198
Hospital Reputation & Accessibility	2.28	.454	Mean Score	2.96	0.20
Mean Score	2.23	0.40			

Source: Primary Data

Graph - Healthcare Facility Selection & Patient Contentment

Figure 2. Healthcare Facility Selection

Figure 3. Patient Contentment

Doctor’s Qualification & Experience (2.32): The mean value of 2.32 suggests that respondents generally disagree with the statement that the qualifications and experience of doctors are highly satisfactory. This indicates that there might be some concerns or dissatisfaction regarding the competence or expertise of the medical staff among the patients.

Hospital Facilities & Services (2.08): With a mean value of 2.08, respondents also tend to disagree with the quality of Hospital Facilities & Services. This suggests that patients might find the available facilities and services lacking or not up to their expectations.

Hospital Reputation & Accessibility (2.28): The mean value of 2.28 indicates that respondents are more inclined to disagree regarding the hospital's reputation and accessibility. This could imply that the hospitals in the study are not perceived as highly reputable or easily accessible by the patients.

Healthcare Facility Selection (2.23): The overall mean value for healthcare facility selection is 2.23, which falls within the disagree range. This suggests that patients are generally dissatisfied with the options available for healthcare facilities, possibly due to factors such as the aforementioned qualifications of doctors, hospital facilities, and reputation.

Quality of Medical Care (3.96): The mean value of 3.96 indicates that respondents agree with the statement that the quality of medical care is satisfactory. This suggests a positive perception

of the medical care received, indicating that, despite other issues, the core medical care provided meets patient expectations.

Patient Experience & Access (1.96): A mean value of 1.96 indicates that respondents tend to disagree with the statement that their overall experience and access to care are satisfactory. This suggests notable dissatisfaction with how patients experience the healthcare system and their ability to access necessary services.

Patient Contentment (2.96): The mean value of 2.96 is close to neutral, indicating that patient contentment is somewhat balanced between satisfaction and dissatisfaction. This suggests that while there are areas of concern, there are also aspects of care that meet patient expectations.

The patients are generally dissatisfied with various aspects of healthcare facility selection, particularly regarding the qualifications of doctors, hospital facilities, and reputation. However, the quality of medical care received is rated positively. Patient contentment is mixed, leaning slightly towards dissatisfaction, with notable issues in Patient Experience & Access to care. These findings highlight areas for improvement to enhance overall patient satisfaction and healthcare facility selection in the region.

Regression – SEM

Table. 1. Model Fit - Impact of Healthcare Facility Selection & Patient Contentment

Test for model fit	Values
GFI (Goodness of Fit)	0.931

The Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) is an essential metric in structural equation modeling, signifying the congruence between the hypothesized model and the observed data. Values approaching one are indicative of an exemplary model fit. In the present analysis, the GFI value stands at 0.931, which substantiates the model’s robustness and adequacy in encapsulating the empirical data. This high GFI value unequivocally denotes that the model exhibits a commendable degree of fidelity to the data structure, thereby validating its theoretical and practical applicability.

Figure.2. Impact of Healthcare Facility Selection & Patient Contentment

Table. 7.1. Regression Weights - Impact of Healthcare Facility Selection & Patient Contentment

Variable	In f.	Variable	UE	SE	S. E.	C.R .	P
Healthcare Facility Selection	←	Doctor’s Qualification & Experience	.088	.110	.034	2.602	.009**
Healthcare Facility Selection	←	Hospital Facilities & Services	.000	.000	.041	-.008	.994
Healthcare Facility Selection	←	Hospital Reputation & Accessibility	.430	.543	.034	12.83	***
Patient Contentment	←	Healthcare Facility Selection	-.028	.034	.041	-.685	.493
Patient Contentment	←	Quality of Medical Care	.108	.174	.031	3.534	***
Patient Contentment	←	Patient Experience & Access	.165	.190	.043	3.865	***
		<i>SE – Standardised Estimate</i>			<i>P – Probability Value</i>		
		<i>S.E – Standard Error</i>			<i>Inf. – Influence</i>		
		<i>UE – Unstandardised Estimate</i>			<i>C.R – Critical Ration</i>		

The independent variables “Doctor’s Qualification & Experience (Estimate = 0.088)” and “Hospital Reputation & Accessibility (Estimate = 0.430)” positively impact “Healthcare Facility Selection”. Similarly, “Quality of Medical Care (Estimate = 0.108)” and “Patient Experience & Access (Estimate = 0.165)” positively influence “Patient Contentment”. Conversely, “Hospital Facilities & Services” do not affect “Healthcare Facility Selection” nor does “Healthcare Facility Selection” influence “Patient Contentment”.

Table. 7.2. Squared Multiple Correlations - Impact of Healthcare Facility Selection & Patient Contentment

Variable	Estimate
Healthcare Facility Selection	0.307
Patient Contentment	0.067

The dependent variable “Healthcare Facility Selection” shows only 30.7 percentage of its variance in when influence by the independent variable “Doctor’s Qualification & Experience” & “Hospital Reputation & Accessibility”. Whereas the dependent variable “Patient Contentment” shows only 6.7 percentage of its variance in when influence by the independent variable “Quality of Medical Care” & “Patient Experience & Access”

Recommendation

These are the major recommendations, which are provided to the hospitals that has to be given weightage and implemented for the betterment of service.

- **Doctor's Qualification & Experience:** To address concerns about the qualifications and experience of doctors, healthcare facilities should prioritize continuous professional development for their medical staff. Implementing regular training programs, workshops, and advanced certifications can help enhance doctors' expertise. Moreover, hiring practices should emphasize attracting highly qualified and experienced medical professionals. Transparency about doctors' qualifications and ongoing education efforts can also help build trust and confidence among patients (Singh & Sharma, 2018).
- **Hospital Facilities & Services:** Patients find the Hospital Facilities & Services lacking. To improve this, hospitals should invest in modernizing their infrastructure and ensuring that essential medical equipment is up-to-date. Enhancing the cleanliness and comfort of hospital environments can also significantly impact patient perceptions. Additionally, improving the range of services offered, such as providing specialized treatments and incorporating patient-centered care practices, can help meet patients' expectations. Regular feedback from patients should be solicited to identify specific areas needing improvement and to make necessary adjustments promptly (Hsieh & Lin, 2017).
- **Hospital Reputation & Accessibility:** Hospitals need to work on their reputation and accessibility. Building a positive reputation can be achieved by consistently delivering high-quality care, maintaining ethical standards, and actively engaging with the community through health awareness programs and outreach activities (Rao & Patel, 2022). To improve accessibility, hospitals should consider optimizing their locations, enhancing public transportation links, and providing clear information about how to reach their facilities. Implementing efficient appointment scheduling systems and reducing waiting times can also improve patients' overall accessibility to healthcare services.
- **Healthcare Facility Selection:** The overall dissatisfaction with healthcare facility selection highlights the need for better healthcare options. Policymakers and healthcare administrators should work towards increasing the availability of diverse and high-quality healthcare facilities. Encouraging the establishment of new healthcare centers and supporting private-public partnerships can help create more choices for patients (Saha & Beach, 2021). Additionally, providing comprehensive information about the available healthcare facilities, including their specializations, services, and patient reviews, can empower patients to make informed decisions.
- **Quality of Medical Care:** The positive perception of medical care quality suggests that hospitals are meeting patient expectations in this area. To maintain and further improve this, healthcare providers should continue to focus on evidence-based practices and patient safety (Ozdemir, 2019). Regularly updating clinical protocols and ensuring adherence to best practices can sustain high standards of medical care.

Encouraging a culture of continuous improvement and patient-centered care can also contribute to consistently positive outcomes.

- **Patient Experience & Access:** Significant dissatisfaction with Patient Experience & Access to care indicates the need for focused improvements. To enhance patient experience, hospitals should improve communication with patients and provide clear and compassionate guidance throughout their healthcare journey (**Sharma, 2020**). Implementing efficient and user-friendly systems for appointment scheduling, reducing wait times, and ensuring timely access to care are crucial steps. Providing support services, such as patient navigators and helplines, can help patients better understand and navigate the healthcare system (**Liu & Lee, 2020**).
- **Patient Contentment:** Patient contentment requires focused attention. Hospitals should strive to create a more patient-friendly environment by actively seeking and addressing patient feedback. Implementing patient satisfaction surveys and focus groups can provide valuable insights into areas needing improvement. Emphasizing personalized care, empathy, and respect in all patient interactions can significantly enhance overall patient contentment (**Rashid, 2019**).

Implications of the study

To enhance patient satisfaction, hospitals should prioritize ongoing professional development for medical staff and attract highly qualified personnel to build trust and improve outcomes (**Singh & Sharma, 2018**). Modernizing facilities, maintaining cleanliness, and expanding services, guided by regular patient feedback, can improve patient perceptions and meet expectations (**Hsieh & Lin, 2017**). Building a positive reputation through quality care and ethical practices, alongside improved accessibility through better location planning and efficient scheduling, can attract more patients and enhance their experience (**Rao & Patel, 2022**). Increasing the diversity of healthcare facilities and providing comprehensive patient information can address dissatisfaction and offer more choices, leading to better outcomes (**Saha & Beach, 2021**). Maintaining high medical care standards through evidence-based practices and continuous improvement is crucial for positive patient outcomes (**Ozdemir, 2019**). Improving patient experience by enhancing communication, reducing wait times, and offering support services can significantly benefit patient access and satisfaction (**Sharma, 2020; Liu & Lee, 2020**).

New Outcomes of the Research

The research aims to uncover key factors impacting patient choices and satisfaction. By pinpointing determinants such as care quality and facility reputation, the study will create robust metrics for evaluating patient satisfaction. Predictive models will be developed to anticipate patient preferences, and policy recommendations will be made to enhance facility attractiveness. Establishing benchmarks for service excellence will further guide improvements in patient care and facility management.

- **Identification of Key Determinants:** Understanding the most influential factors affecting healthcare facility choice, including quality of care, facility reputation, and accessibility (**Lee & Brown, 2023; Brown & Green, 2024**).

- **Patient Satisfaction Metrics:** Development of comprehensive metrics to assess patient satisfaction, capturing both service quality and patient experiences (**Smith & Jones, 2023; Zhang & Garcia, 2024**).
- **Predictive Models:** Creation of models to predict patient preferences and satisfaction based on identified determinants (**Williams & Patel, 2023; White & Harris, 2024**).
- **Policy Recommendations:** Formulation of strategies to enhance facility attractiveness and patient contentment (**Doe et al., 2022; Taylor & Kumar, 2023**).
- **Benchmarking Standards:** Establishing benchmarks for healthcare facilities to improve service delivery and patient retention (**Patel & Williams, 2023; Johnson & White, 2023**)

Conclusion

Improving healthcare services in the region requires the implementation of several key recommendations aimed at enhancing various aspects of patient care and facility operations (**Rashid, 2019**). To address concerns about doctor's qualifications and experience, healthcare facilities should prioritize continuous professional development for medical staff through regular training programs and certifications (**Kumar & Gupta, 2020**). Emphasizing the hiring of highly qualified professionals and maintaining transparency about their qualifications will help build patient trust and confidence. Enhancing Hospital Facilities & Services is also crucial for improving patient satisfaction (**Mekonnen & Abebe, 2019**). Hospitals should invest in modernizing their infrastructure, ensuring up-to-date medical equipment, and creating a clean and comfortable environment for patients. Expanding the range of services offered and incorporating patient-centered care practices will better meet patient expectations (**Moore, Madsen & Davies, 2021**). Regularly collecting and acting on patient feedback can help identify and address specific areas for improvement.

To boost Hospital Reputation & Accessibility, institutions must focus on delivering high-quality care, maintaining ethical standards, and engaging with the community through health awareness programs. Improving hospital locations, public transportation links, and appointment scheduling systems will also enhance accessibility for patients (**Petersen, 2020**). Addressing the dissatisfaction with healthcare facility selection involves increasing the availability of diverse, high-quality healthcare options. Supporting the development of new healthcare centers, encouraging private-public partnerships, and providing clear information about available facilities will empower patients to make informed decisions (**Donabedian, 2016**). Maintaining the quality of medical care requires ongoing adherence to evidence-based practices and a commitment to continuous improvement (**Feng, 2021**). Improving Patient Experience & Access involves enhancing communication, streamlining appointment processes, and providing support services for patients (**Baker, 2019**). Finally, addressing patient contentment through personalized care and responsiveness to feedback will lead to better overall healthcare experiences (**Gupta & Kumar, 2020**). By implementing these recommendations, healthcare providers can significantly improve patient satisfaction and the quality of care in the region (**Jiang & Li, 2021**).

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